

DESIGN OF THE THERMAL TRANSPORT IN FIBER REINFORCED COMPOSITES

V. V. Deshpande^{1,2}, R. Piat^{1*}, Y. Sinchuk¹, G. Stasiuk¹ P. Mahajan²

¹Institute of Engineering Mechanics, KIT
Karlsruhe, Germany

²Indian Institute of Technology, Department of Applied Mechanics,
Hauz Khas, New Delhi, India

* Corresponding author (romana.piat@kit.edu)

1 Introduction

A composite material with prescribed material properties can serve many critical industrial applications. Reduced weight, increased stiffness, optimized thermal conductivities and thermal expansion coefficients of a composite specimen can be achieved by optimizing the microstructure of the composite material with respect to different objective functions. A considerable research work has been done over the years to optimize the design components so as to meet the specified needs of the application. Topology optimization has been extensively explored to develop innovative conceptual designs. A review of such methods is presented in M.P. Bendsoe et al [1]. Optimised thermal expansion coefficients using a three phase topology optimization have been studied by O. Sigmund et al [2]. R. Piat et al [3] and G. Stasiuk et al [4] have extended this technology to microstructure (fiber volume fraction and fiber orientation) optimization of composites subjected to mechanical loading.

Optimization of microstructure of composites with respect to thermal loading is an equally important field of research with its applications ranging from underbody of a spaceship and nose cone of missiles to components of a reactor producing carbon-carbon composites. The heat generated in such applications is required to be transferred to a sink in a controlled manner so that the components maintain their properties and the heat does not destroy the sensitive circuitry that is present in the vicinity of these components. For

example, carbon-carbon composites and silicon carbide composites are suitable in aerospace applications because of their high thermal conductivity and stable mechanical properties under high temperature loading. As such, designing the microstructure of such composites would enhance their usage in such applications.

The optimization procedure requires numerical or analytical homogenization methods to determine the effective thermal conductivity of the composite. J.D. Thornburgh et al [5] derived an analogy with an electrical circuit to determine the longitudinal and transverse thermal conductivity of the unidirectional fiber composite. Effective thermal conductivity of the composite with imperfect interface was studied by D.P.H. Hasselman et al [6]. Bounds on thermal conductivity of fiber composites with isotropic constituents were given by S. Nomura et al [7]. An effective medium approximation known as Mori-Tanaka scheme was studied by H.J. Böhm et al [8] to determine the thermal conductivity of the composite. It is based upon an equivalent inclusion problem for steady state heat conduction in the composite which has been solved by H. Hatta et al [9].

In this paper, microstructure of a two-dimensional specimen made up of a fibrous composite is optimized for a problem of thermal loading. In this problem, the temperature of hotspot i.e, the maximum temperature of the specimen is minimized. The design variable in the optimization problem is the fiber angle orientation.

2. Material model

Mori-Tanaka scheme for unidirectional fibrous composites is used in this paper to determine the effective thermal conductivity of the composite material. According to this scheme, the effective conductivity tensor for a multiphase composite is given by, (refer H. J. Böhm et al [8]).

$$\mathbf{K}^H = \mathbf{K}_0 + \sum_{r=1}^N v_r (\mathbf{K}_r - \mathbf{K}_0) \cdot \mathbf{A}_r \cdot \quad (1)$$

Where

$$\bar{\mathbf{H}}_r = \mathbf{A}_r \cdot \bar{\mathbf{H}},$$

$$\mathbf{A}_r = \mathbf{T}_r \cdot \left(\sum_{n=0}^N v_n \mathbf{T}_n \right)^{-1},$$

$$\mathbf{T}_n = \left[\mathbf{S}_n \cdot \mathbf{K}_0^{-1} \cdot (\mathbf{K}_n - \mathbf{K}_0) + \mathbf{I} \right]^{-1}.$$

Here \mathbf{K}^H is the effective thermal conductivity tensor of the composite material, \mathbf{K} is the thermal conductivity tensor of constituents, N is the number of inhomogeneities present in the composite, v is volume fraction of the constituents, $\bar{\mathbf{H}}$ is average temperature gradient of the entire composite whereas $\bar{\mathbf{H}}_r$ is that of the r -th inhomogeneity, \mathbf{A}_r is the gradient concentration tensor of the individual inhomogeneities, \mathbf{S} is the Eshelby like tensor of the individual inhomogeneities derived by H. Hatta et al [9] and \mathbf{I} is 2nd order identity tensor. Subscript 0 corresponds to properties of the matrix and subscripts r and n correspond to properties of the r -th and n -th inhomogeneity respectively.

The composites studied here are assumed to be perfect composites, i.e, without porosity and cracks.

3. Optimization problem

Following is the detailed discussion of the optimization problem of the thermal loading.

3.1 Governing equation

The governing equation for the steady state two-dimensional heat conduction problem defined in material region Ω ,

$$-\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{k} \nabla T) = f,$$

where \mathbf{k} denote thermal conductivity tensor, f is the heat energy generated per unit volume, ∇T is temperature gradient.

Equation (1) in finite element formulation is

$$\mathbf{KT} = \mathbf{F} \quad (2)$$

Where \mathbf{K} is the global thermal conductivity matrix, \mathbf{T} is the nodal temperature vector and \mathbf{F} is the applied heat vector. Consider no internal heat generation in the material region Ω (i.e, $f = 0$).

3.2 Minimization of the maximum temperature of the composite specimen

3.2.1 Formulation

The two-dimensional material region (Fig. 1) is discretized into four noded quadrilateral elements. Since the effective thermal conductivity of the specimen due to anisotropy of the composite constituents is a function of fiber orientation angle $\theta = \theta(x, y)$, $(x, y) \in \Omega$, each element of the mesh has its own fiber orientation.

The goal of the optimization is to find the minimum of the highest local temperature in the specimen for the given applied thermal boundary conditions. In Y. Zhang et al [10], it was shown that this problem can be reformulated into an equivalent one with objective function

$$D = -\frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (\nabla T)^T \mathbf{q} d\Omega,$$

where D is dissipation of heat transport potential capacity of the entire specimen and $\mathbf{q} = -\mathbf{k} \nabla T$ is the heat flux.

The optimization problem is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\theta} D_h(\theta) \\ & \text{s.t. } \mathbf{KT} = \mathbf{F}, \\ & 0 \leq \theta_e \leq \pi, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $D_h = \mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{T}$, $\theta = \{\theta_e\}$ is the vector of the fiber orientation angles in each element e .

The fiber orientation angle in all the elements is assumed as 0° before the start of the optimization process. With each iteration, this angle is updated in order to minimize the objective function.

3.2.2 Sensitivity analysis

The objective function is differentiated with respect to the design variable (refer Y. Zhang et al [10]):

$$\frac{\partial D_h}{\partial \theta_e} = \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta_e} [\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{T}] = -T_e^T \frac{\partial K(\theta_e)}{\partial \theta_e} T_e. \quad (4)$$

Necessary condition of extremum of the objective function for each element e defined in region Ω_e , (refer Y. Zhang et al [10]) can be written in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial D_h}{\partial \theta_e} &= - \int_{\Omega_e} T_e^T B^T \frac{\partial k_{\theta_e}}{\partial \theta_e} B T_e de = \\ &= \int_{\Omega_e} T_e^T B^T k_{\theta_e} \frac{\partial k_{\theta_e}^{-1}}{\partial \theta_e} k_{\theta_e} B T_e de \approx q_e^T \frac{\partial k_{\theta_e}^{-1}}{\partial \theta_e} q_e, \end{aligned}$$

where D_e is the dissipation of heat transport potential capacity in an element defined in region Ω_e , B is the matrix of derivatives of shape functions, T_e is the nodal temperature vector of the element, q_e is the heat flux vector of the element

such that $q_e = \frac{1}{4} \left(\sum_{i=1}^4 k_{\theta_e} B_i T_e \right)$, where $i = 1, \dots, 4$ are

indexes of the integration points in the element and k_{θ_e} is the thermal conductivity matrix which is a function of fiber orientation angle in the element e .

Here $k_{\theta_e} = k(\theta_e) = Q(\theta_e) k' Q^T(\theta_e)$, where

$$Q(\theta_e) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_e) & -\sin(\theta_e) \\ \sin(\theta_e) & \cos(\theta_e) \end{bmatrix}$$

is transformation matrix and k' is thermal conductivity matrix in material coordinate system.

Therefore, the necessary optimality condition in each element is,

$$q_e^T \frac{\partial k_{\theta_e}^{-1}}{\partial \theta_e} q_e = 0.$$

Solving it we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial D_h}{\partial \theta_e} &= (k_1^{-1} - k_2^{-1}) \times \\ & [2q_x q_y \cos 2\theta_e - (q_x^2 - q_y^2) \sin 2\theta_e] = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

k_1 and k_2 are components of k' and q_x and q_y are the components of the heat flux vector q_e for each element. From eqn. (5),

$$\tan 2\theta_e = \frac{2q_x q_y}{q_x^2 - q_y^2} = \frac{2 \tan \theta_e}{1 - \tan^2 \theta_e}.$$

So,

$$\tan \theta_e = \frac{q_y}{q_x} \text{ or } -\frac{q_x}{q_y}, \quad (6)$$

The sufficiency condition following,

$$\frac{\partial^2 D_e}{\partial \theta_e^2} = -2(k_1^{-1} - k_2^{-1})A > 0 \quad (7)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} A &= (q_x^2 - q_y^2) \cos 2\theta_e + 2q_x q_y \sin 2\theta_e = \\ &= (q_x^2 - q_y^2) \cos 2\theta_e (1 + \tan^2 2\theta_e) = \\ &= (q_x^2 - q_y^2) \cos^2 \theta_e (1 - \tan^2 \theta_e) (1 + \tan^2 2\theta_e). \end{aligned}$$

Therefore for $k_1 > k_2$, the sufficiency minimum condition $(q_x^2 - q_y^2)(1 - \tan^2 \theta_e) > 0$ is fulfilled only for $\tan \theta_e = \frac{q_y}{q_x}$. So, $\theta_e = \tan^{-1} \frac{q_y}{q_x}$.

This criterion for fiber orientation angle shows that the fibre in each element should be aligned in the direction of the heat flux vector q_e (shown in Fig. 2).

3.3 Numerical results

3.3.1 Material model and verification

The Mori-Tanaka scheme used to model the effective thermal conductivity of the material is verified by using the experimental data of unidirectional carbon-epoxy composite given in M.W. Pilling et al [11]. The thermal conductivity of fiber and matrix is taken from the same reference. The composite considered here have negligent amount of porosity and hence the porosity is neglected in the mathematical models as well.

The Figs. 3a and 3b show that in case of transverse thermal conductivity of the composite, the results obtained by Mori-Tanaka and Hassleman-Johnson Model (refer D.P.H. Hasselman et al [6]) give the same result and are in compliance with the experimental data as well. The Electric-Resistance Analogy (refer J.D. Thornburgh et al [5]) gives a lower estimate of the transverse conductivity. In the case of axial thermal conductivity of the composite, all the models give the same results and are in compliance with the experimental data as well.

3.3.2 Microstructure optimization

In this problem, a two dimensional rectangular specimen is subjected to a uniformly distributed heat flux, $Q = 200 \text{ kW/m}$ as shown in the Fig. 4a. A fixed temperature of $T = 273.15 \text{ K}$ is maintained at two locations of the specimen. The remaining entire boundary region is adiabatic.

Fig. 4c shows that the maximum temperature in the specimen which occurs at a point shown by a black solid marker is reduced during the optimization process. The composite studied in this

problem is a carbon composite with pyrolytic matrix. The thermal conductivity of the fiber is taken from J.W. Klett et al [12] and of matrix from our previous studies. The fiber volume fraction is considered 0.4 and the composite is without porosity.

Fig. 5 shows that the maximum temperature of the specimen for the given problem has been reduced from 278.23 K to 276.25 K during the optimization.

3.3.4 Discrete fiber angle orientation

Sometimes it is difficult to manufacture a composite having a curved fiber embedded in it. To cater to this manufacturing difficulty, an attempt has been made to see how the temperature distribution and fiber orientation varies when the fiber orientation angle is not allowed to vary continuously, i.e. to take any possible angle, but to vary discretely, i.e. to take angles in specified steps.

For example, if the orientation angle step is decided as 15° , then the angle obtained from iteration, lying in range of 7.5° to 15° will take angle value of 15° and that in the range of 0° to 7.4° will take the angle value of 0° . This is explained in Fig. 6.

This discrete fiber orientation angle scheme is applied to the optimization problem.

Figs. 7a to 7d show the variation of fiber orientation angle and temperature distribution as the angle step is increased from 15° to 90° . Fig. 8 shows that as the angle step is increased, the maximum temperature of the specimen obtained after optimization is increased from 276.25 K for continuous angle variation to 277.23 K for angle step of 90° .

4. Conclusions

This study presents microstructure optimization of a two dimensional fiber composite specimen for the problem of heat conduction.

The main results obtained are the following:

1. The maximum temperature of the specimen is minimised by orienting the fibers embedded in it in optimal angles.
2. The fiber angle orientation need not be varying continuously in space inside the composite. Even if the fibers are oriented with discrete angles,

the temperatures in the specimen (maximum temperature of the specimen or mean temperature of a specified region of the specimen) are reduced during optimization. However, this reduction in temperature is not as much as that obtained by varying the fiber angle orientation continuously.

3. This study can be used to manufacture composites with continuous fibers arranged in a curved path inside the composite. The manufacturing difficulty of orienting the fibers in a curve path can be resolved by orienting the fiber in discrete angles.

Fig. 1. A material region Ω , with boundary S , subjected to heat flux q and temperature boundary condition $T = t_0$. The remaining boundary S is adiabatic.

Fig. 2. Orientation of fiber with respect to x -axis in each element

Table 1
Thermal conductivity of fiber and matrix
(M.W.Pilling et al [11])

Thermal conductivities(W/mK)	K_r	K_θ	K_z
Fiber	1.7	1.7	9
Matrix	0.19	0.19	0.19

Fig. 3. Variation of (a) transverse thermal conductivity (K_T^*) and (b) axial thermal conductivity (K_A^*) of composite with respect to fiber volume fraction obtained by Mori-Tanaka scheme, Hasselman-Johnson, Electric-Resistance and the experimental data.

Fig. 4. (a) Geometry and BC of the problem defined for optimization. Fiber angle orientation and temperature distribution (b) before optimization and (c) after optimization

Fig. 5. Variation of maximum temperature of the specimen with iterations

Fig. 6. Orientation of fiber with respect to x -axis in each element

Fig. 7. (a)-(d) Fiber orientation angle and temperature distribution in the specimen for different angle steps.

Fig. 8. Variation of maximum temperature of the specimen with respect to no of iterations for different steps of fiber orientation angle.

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